

SYMPOSIUM PROGRAM

EMAIL

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21-esfc-lisbon.events.chemistry.pt

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General Information: Lisbon

Lisbon was awarded by the [World Travel Awards](#) as Europe's Leading City Destination 2024. It is the capital of Portugal and a historical city full of stories to tell, where the sun shines 290 days a year and the temperature rarely drops below 15 °C. A city where you feel safe wandering around day or night, where the cuisine is dedicated to creating over a thousand ways to cook the beloved *bacalhau* (salted cod), and where you will find hotels and restaurants to suit every taste, budget and requirement. Discover Lisbon, a city full of authenticity where old customs and ancient history intermix with cultural entertainment and hi-tech innovation. Lisbon is ageless, but it loves company, as you will find out if you meet someone and ask them to explain, with lots of gestures and repetition, where the best place is to listen to *Fado*. After all, Lisbon is famous for its hospitality and the family-like way it welcomes visitors.

Please find further information about Lisbon's top attractions, events, restaurants, hotels and more on this official website: <https://www.visitlisboa.com/>.

Time Zone: The time zone in Lisbon is WEST (summer) and GMT (winter).

Water: Tap water in Portugal is safe drinking water!

Electricity: Standard voltage is 220V AC. Plugs are European style with two round pins.

Currency, Banks and Post Offices: The national currency in Portugal is the Euro. Banks are open from Monday to Friday between 8:30 a.m. and 3 p.m. Post offices are usually open between 8:30 a.m. and 6 p.m. Exchange houses operate every day between 9 a.m. and 1 p.m. and from 2 p.m. to 7 p.m.

Programme Summary

Sunday, August 3, 2025			Room
9:00	13:00	Excursion Sintra & Cascais	-
14:30	18:30	Registration	Pavilion 3
16:30	18:30	Opening Session	Auditorium II
17:15	18:15	Plenary Session - Pierangelo Metrangolo	Auditorium II
18:30	20:30	Welcome Reception	In front of Auditorium II

Monday, August 4, 2025			Room
8:30	18:30	Registration	Pavilion 3
9:00	10:00	Plenary Session - Mark Shiflett	Auditorium II
10:00	10:45	Keynote Session - Marie-Pierre Krafft	Auditorium II
10:45	11:15	Coffee Break & Exhibition	Pavilion 3
11:15	13:30	Parallel sessions I (see program)	
13:30	14:30	Lunch Break	
14:30	16:30	Parallel sessions II (see program)	
16:30	17:00	Coffee Break & Exhibition	Pavilion 3
17:00	18:30	Parallel sessions III (see program)	

Tuesday, August 5, 2025			Room
8:30	18:30	Registration	Pavilion 3
9:00	10:00	Plenary Session - Veronique Gouverneur	Auditorium II
10:00	10:45	Keynote Session - Beate Kokschi	Auditorium II
10:45	10:50	Group Photo	Stairs between Auditorium II and Pavilion 3
10:50	11:15	Coffee Break & Exhibition	Pavilion 3
11:15	13:30	Public Discussion About PFAS	Auditorium II
13:30	14:30	Lunch Break	
14:30	18:30	Excursion Belém & Jerónimos/ Events and activities organised by European projects MAR2PROTECT, ALERT-PFAS and LIFE4FGASES	Pavilion 3

Wednesday, August 6, 2025			Room
8:30	18:30	Registration	Pavilion 3
9:00	10:00	Plenary Session - Dexi Weng	Auditorium II
10:00	10:45	Keynote Session - Matthew Hopkinson	Auditorium II
10:45	11:15	Coffee Break & Exhibition	Pavilion 3
11:15	13:30	Parallel sessions IV (see program)	
13:30	14:30	Lunch Break	
14:30	17:15	Parallel sessions V (see program)	
17:15	19:30	Poster Session	Pavilion 3

Thursday, August 7, 2025			Room
8:30	18:30	Registration	Pavilion 3
9:00	10:00	Plenary Session - Feng-Ling Qing	Auditorium II
10:00	10:45	Keynote Session - Berthold Hoge	Auditorium II
10:45	11:15	Coffee Break & Exhibition	Pavilion 3
11:15	13:30	Parallel sessions VI (see program)	
13:30	14:30	Lunch Break	
14:30	16:30	Parallel sessions VII (see program)	
16:30	17:00	Coffee Break & Exhibition	Pavilion 3
17:00	18:30	Flash Presentations (see program)	Auditorium II
20:00	23:00	Conference Dinner	Restaurant SUD

Friday, August 8, 2025			Room
8:30	13:30	Registration	Pavilion 3
9:00	10:00	Plenary Session - Florian Kraus	Auditorium II
10:00	10:45	Keynote Session - Cormac Murphy	Auditorium II
10:45	11:15	Coffee Break & Exhibition	Pavilion 3
11:15	12:00	Keynote Session - Kazuhiko Matsumoto	Auditorium II
12:00	13:00	Plenary Session - Petr Beier	Auditorium II
13:00	14:30	Closing Session + Awards	Auditorium II
15:30	19:30	Excursion Alfama	-

Saturday, August 9, 2025		
9:30	17:30	Excursion Sintra & Cascais

Welcoming Message

Dear Colleagues,

On behalf of the Organising Committee, we welcome you to the 21st European Symposium on Fluorine Chemistry in Lisbon, Portugal.

The European Symposium on Fluorine Chemistry (ESFC) brings together industrial and academic fluorine chemists from around the world and was first held in Munich in 1965. The conference is held every three years in Europe, and the event and scientific program cover all topics related to fluorine technologies and fluorine chemistry.

The 21st European Symposium on Fluorine Chemistry will be held in Lisbon, Portugal, hosted by the NOVA School of Science and Technology and LAQV/REQUIMTE in partnership with the Portuguese Society of Chemistry (SPQ). The ESFC LISBON will bring together large numbers of international researchers from academia, research institutes, and industry. The scientific program offers forums that encompass a wide range of applied and fundamental fluorine chemistry. It will offer insights from physical and theoretical chemistry, as well as the fields of fluorine technologies, sustainable processes, biomedicine, and materials science, among others.

We look forward to an outstanding program filled with engaging scientific discussions, as well as the opportunity for you to experience the rich history, vibrant culture, and natural beauty of Lisbon and Portugal.

The 21st ESFC Chairs:

Ana B. Pereiro

LAQV/REQUIMTE, NOVA School of Science and Technology (NOVA FCT), NOVA University Lisbon, Portugal

João M. M. Araújo

LAQV/REQUIMTE, NOVA School of Science and Technology (NOVA FCT), NOVA University Lisbon, Portugal

Committees

Conference Chairs

Ana B. Pereiro and João M. M. Araújo

LAQV/REQUIMTE, NOVA School of Science and Technology (NOVA FCT), NOVA University Lisbon, Portugal

Organizing Committee

Beatriz Pereira Machado - LAQV/REQUIMTE, NOVA FCT

Clara S. B. Gomes - LAQV/REQUIMTE, NOVA FCT

Inês Matos - LAQV/REQUIMTE, NOVA FCT

Joana C. Bastos - LAQV/REQUIMTE, NOVA FCT

Julio Eduardo Sosa Parra - LAQV/REQUIMTE, NOVA FCT

Márcia Ventura - LAQV/REQUIMTE, NOVA FCT

Maria Bernardo - LAQV/REQUIMTE, NOVA FCT

Maria Camila Naranjo - LAQV/REQUIMTE, NOVA FCT

Maria Vaz - LAQV/REQUIMTE, NOVA FCT

Srdana Kolakovic Oliveira Barreiros - LAQV/REQUIMTE, NOVA FCT

Scientific Committee

Beate Kocsch, Germany

Bruno Ameduri, France

David O'Hagan, UK

Joseph Thrasher, USA

Marie Pierre Krafft, France

Michael Gerken, Canada

Norio Shibata, Japan

Olga Boltalina, USA

Pierangelo Metrangolo, Italy

Thomas Braun, Germany

Véronique Gouverneur, UK

Wojciech Grochala, Poland

International Advisory Board

Carlos Jacinto, Brazil
David A. Dixon, USA
Deepak Chopra, India
Erhard Kemnitz, Germany
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Gašper Tavčar, Slovenia
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Miguel Baya García, Spain
Miroslav Boča, Slovakia
Norman Lu, Taiwan
Petr Beier, Czech Republic
Rimantas Knizikevičius, Lithuania
Sebastian Hasenstab-Riedel, Germany
Shlomo Rozen, Israel
Timothy Noël, Netherlands

Venue and Maps

The Lisbon Congress Centre (CCL) is located next to the Tagus River, close to the historic and cultural heritage area of Belém, just a few minutes from the city centre. This area benefits from a wide range of transport options, and it is a welcoming space to carry out congresses, conferences, business meetings, fairs, parties, exhibitions and other events.

Address:

Praça das Industrias, 1

1300-307 Lisbon, Portugal

GROUND FLOOR | Pavilion 3, Rooms 3A, 3B and 3C

FIRST FLOOR | Auditorium II

Technical Information

WIFI

SSID: ESFC LISBON

Password: ch3m!LX25

LECTURES

Length

Plenary Lecture | PL | 60 min

Keynote | KN | 45 min

Invited Lecture | IL | 20 min

Oral communication | Oral | 15 min

Flash presentation | FP | 5 min

Please help keep our conference programme on schedule by adhering to these time limits.

Delivery of data for presentations

Please prepare your PowerPoint presentations in 16:9 format and submit them to email esfc.lisbon@chemistry.pt before the start of the conference. Alternatively, you may deliver them in person in the designated presentation room, no later than the session preceding your own.

POSTER SESSION

Wednesday, August 6th, 2025 | 17:15 – 19:30

Room: Pavilion 3

Posters can be mounted from the morning of August 6th. The poster session of the 6th will be accompanied by a light dinner. The posters will be

exhibited from August 6th to August 8th. Each poster has been assigned a number, which will also be displayed on the movable wall. Our friendly ESFC LISBON staff will be on hand to assist you in finding your designated poster spot and will provide mounting material as well as assistance. Please remember to remove your posters at the end of the conference.

SOCIAL PROGRAMME

Welcome Reception | Sunday, August 4th, 2025 | 18:30 – 20:30

After gathering in Auditorium II for the opening session and the first plenary lecture of ESFC LISBON 2025, we will

move to the welcome reception that will take place **in front of Auditorium II.**

Conference Dinner | Thursday, August 7th, 2025 | 20:00 – 23:00

The Conference Dinner will be held at the **SUD Lisboa Hall**. Situated in the

iconic Belém district of Lisbon, this venue seamlessly blends modernity,

sophistication, and innovation, ensuring every event is truly one of a kind. Just a 15-minute walk from the conference

venue (CCL), it offers a scenic riverside route with breathtaking views of Lisbon's stunning 25th of April Bridge.

Group Photo

Tuesday, August 5th, 2025 | 10:45 – 10:50

The group photograph is scheduled for Tuesday, August 5th at 10:45 **on the**

stairs between Auditorium II and Pavilion 3.

Scientific Programme: Talks

Sunday, August 3rd, 2025

Sunday

OPENING SESSION

Room: Auditorium II

16:30 – 18:30 **WELCOMING WORDS**

PLENARY SESSION - PIERANGELO METRANGOLO

Room: Auditorium II

Chair: Ana B. Pereiro and João M. M. Araújo, NOVA FCT, Portugal

17:15 – 18:15 **INTERMOLECULAR RECOGNITION PHENOMENA INVOLVING POLY-FLUOROALKYL AMPHIPHILES**

PL **Pierangelo Metrangolo**, Politecnico di Milano, Italy

WELCOME RECEPTION

Room: Auditorium II

18:30 – 20:30 **FIRST FLOOR CCL – IN FRONT OF AUDITORIUM II**

Sunday

Monday, August 4th, 2025

PLENARY SESSION - MARK SHIFLETT

Room: Auditorium II

Chair: Bruno Ameduri, Institute Charles Gerhardt Montpellier, France

09:00 – 10:00 **NSF ENGINEERING RESEARCH CENTER EARTH (ENVIRONMENTALLY APPLIED REFRIGERANT TECHNOLOGY HUB)**

PL **Mark B. Shiflett**, University of Kansas, USA

KEYNOTE SESSION - MARIE-PIERRE KRAFFT

Room: Auditorium II

Chair: Wojciech Grochala, University Warsaw, Poland

10:00 – 10:45 **PER- AND POLYFLUOROALKYL SUBSTANCES (PFAS): A TALE OF TWO FACES FOCUSING ON THE SUPRAMOLECULAR SELF-ASSEMBLING PROPENSITY OF PFAS SURFACTANTS**

KN **Marie Pierre Krafft**, University of Strasbourg, France

PARALLEL SESSION I – ORGANIC CHEMISTRY

Room: Auditorium II

Chair: Dominique Cahard, CNRS, France

11:15 – 11:35 **THE SYNTHESIS AND PROPERTIES OF PARTIALLY FLUORINATED ALIPHATIC MOTIFS FOR APPLICATIONS IN MATERIALS AND PHARMACEUTICALS CHEMISTRY**

IL **David O'Hagan**, University of St Andrews, UK

11:35 – 11:55 **REPURPOSING HFCS: A PATHWAY TOWARD GREENER FLUORINE CHEMISTRY**

IL **Norio Shibata**, Nagoya Institute of Technology, Japan

11:55 – 12:10 **DIVERGENT ACCESS TO SULFUR FLUORINE GROUP-CONTAINING MOLECULES**

Oral **Tim Gatzenmeier**, University of Nebraska-Lincoln, USA

12:10 – 12:25 **SELECTFLUOR PROMOTED DIRECTING GROUP AND TRANSITION METAL CATALYST FREE SITE-SELECTIVE C7 FLUORINATION OF 2-OXINDOLES**

Oral **Madan Kumar**, Indian Institute Of Technology–Ropar (IIT–Ropar), India

12:25 – 12:40 **NEW FLUORINE-CONTAINING PROLINES FOR DRUG DISCOVERY**

Oral **Ivan Kondratov**, Enamine Germany, Germany

12:40 – 12:55 **RADICAL PHOTOCHEMICAL DIFLUOROSULFOXIMINATION OF ALKENES AND PROPELLANES**

Oral **Julien Paut**, University of Paris-Saclay, France

12:55 – 13:10 **RATIONAL DESIGN OF POLYFLUORINATED PEPTIDE-BASED BIOMATERIALS**

Oral **Maurizio Iannuzzi**, Freie Universität Berlin, Germany

Monday

13:10 – 13:25 **TOWARDS A NEW DIRECT METHOD FOR THE SYNTHESIS OF ARYL DIFLUOROALKYL ETHERS FROM THE DIFLUOROMETHOXY (-OCHF₂) MOIETY**

Oral **Guillaume Siegel**, CNRS - Université de Strasbourg, France

PARALLEL SESSION I – INORGANIC CHEMISTRY & COMPUTATIONAL CHEMISTRY

Room: 3A

Chair: Beate Kocsch, Freie University of Berlin, Germany

11:15 – 11:35 **CHEMISTRY OF MOF₅ AND MOOF₃**

IL **Michael Gerken**, University of Lethbridge, Canada

11:35 – 11:55 **METAL FLUORIDE COMPLEXES AS FUNCTIONAL, STRUCTURE-DIRECTING BUILDING BLOCKS IN MOLECULAR MAGNETISM AND BEYOND**

IL **Jesper Bendix**, University of Copenhagen, Denmark

11:55 – 12:10 **PHYSICOCHEMICAL PARAMETERS OF CHEMICAL CAPACITORS FEATURING FLUORINE-RICH OXIDIZERS AND SEPARATORS**

Oral **Łukasz Wolański**, University of Warsaw, Poland

12:10 – 12:25 **NOVEL X_E-N AND X_E-O BONDED CATIONS: FORMATION, STRUCTURE, AND REACTIVITY**

Oral **Kristian Radan**, Jozef Stefan Institute, Slovenia

12:25 – 12:40 **FROM COPPER TO LANTHANIDES: UNIQUE COMPLEXES WITH WEAKLY BOUND LIGANDS AND STABILIZED BY WEAKLY COORDINATING ANIONS**

Oral **Przemysław J. Malinowski**, Centre of New Technologies, University of Warsaw, Poland

12:40 – 12:55 **DECODING THE FLUOROUS EFFECT WITH IR SPECTROSCOPY**

Oral **Ruben Cruz**, Freie Universität Berlin, Germany

12:55 – 13:10 **SUPERCONDUCTIVITY IN LITHIUM HYDRIDE LAYER ENHANCED BY FLUORIDE SUBSTRATES**

Oral **Piotr Szkudlarek**, University of Warsaw, Poland

PARALLEL SESSION I – CONTAMINANTS OF EMERGING CONCERN SPONSORED BY MAR2PROTECT

Room: 3B

Chair: Manuel M. Piñeiro, Universidade de Vigo, Spain

11:15 – 11:30 **IMPLEMENTING LIVINGLABS FOR GROUNDWATER PROTECTION: MAR2PROTECT EXPERIENCES IN EUROPE AND AFRICA**

IL **Uta Wehn**, IHE Delft Institute for Water Education, The Netherlands

11:30 – 11:45 **NATURAL WETLANDS AS NATURE-BASED SOLUTIONS TO REMOVE POLLUTANTS AND PROMOTE THE GOOD QUALITY OF ESTUARINE SURFACE WATER**

IL **C. Marisa R. Almeida**, CIIMAR, Porto University, Portugal

11:45 – 12:00 **REAL-TIME BIOMONITORING OF EMERGING CONTAMINANTS IN WATER RESOURCES**

IL **Gideon Wolfaardt**, Stellenbosch University, South Africa

12:00 – 12:15	INTEGRATED FIXED-BED COLUMN ADSORPTION AND SOLID-STATE FERMENTATION FOR EFFECTIVE REMOVAL OF BISPHENOL A USING BIOCHAR-BASED BIOMATERIALS
IL	Atef Jaouani , University of Tunis El Manar, Tunisia
12:15 – 12:30	NOVEL BIO-BASED ADSORBENTS FOR PFAS REMOVAL: A LIFE CYCLE ASSESSMENT APPROACH
IL	Jolanta Dvarionienė , Kaunas University of Technology, Lithuania
12:30 – 12:45	CHARACTERIZING AND ASSESSING REMOVAL PERFORMANCE OF TARGET NATURAL CONTAMINANTS IN A LAKE-WATER PILOT INSTALLATION IN THE NETHERLANDS
IL	Sergio Salinas , IHE Delft, The Netherlands
12:45 – 12:55	REMOVAL OF PER- AND POLY-FLUOROALKYL SUBSTANCES (PFAS) AND PHARMACEUTICALS ONTO ACTIVATED CARBON FROM WASTEWATER EFFLUENTS
Oral	María C. Naranjo , Nova School of Science of Technology, FCT NOVA, Portugal
12:55 – 13:05	SUITABILITY AND FEASIBILITY MAPPING TO ASSESS MANAGED AQUIFER RECHARGE SOLUTIONS TO COPE WITH GROUNDWATER POLLUTION
Oral	Isabel Gamallo Paz , CETAQUA - Water Technology Center, Spain
13:05 – 13:15	PHARMACEUTICAL REMOVAL FROM WASTEWATER BY ADSORPTION ON COMMERCIAL MATERIALS AND MOLECULARLY IMPRINTED POLYMERS
Oral	Elisa Girometti , University of Bologna, Italy
13:15 – 13:25	PFAS OPTICAL DETECTION APPROACH IN MAR2PROTECT
Oral	Moisés Barata , Instituto de Telecomunicações, Portugal

PARALLEL SESSION II – INORGANIC CHEMISTRY

Room: Auditorium II

Chair: Florian Kraus, Philipps-Universität Marburg, Germany

14:30 – 14:50	A POTPOURRI OF MAIN-GROUP FLUORINE CHEMISTRY
IL	Joseph S. Thrasher , Clemson University, USA
14:50 – 15:05	INVESTIGATION ON THE PENTAFLUOROOSULFATE (-OSF₅) GROUP FOR INORGANIC AND (BIO)ORGANIC APPLICATIONS
Oral	Alexandre Millanvois , Freie Universität Berlin, Germany
15:05 – 15:20	SOLUBILITY INVESTIGATION OF SELECTED RE₂O₃ IN (LiF-NaF)_{EUT} VS (LiF-NaF-REF₃) MOLTEN SYSTEMS
Oral	Blanka Kubíková , Institute of Inorganic Chemistry, Slovak Academy of Sciences, Slovakia
15:20 – 15:35	NEW BORYL AND DIBORATE DIANIONS
Oral	Merlin Bohn , Universität Würzburg, Germany
15:35 – 15:50	CRYSTAL STRUCTURE ELUCIDATION OF XENON COMPOUNDS BY 3D ELECTRON DIFFRACTION ON NANOMETER-SIZED CRYSTALLITES
Oral	Matic Lozinsek , Jozef Stefan Institute, Slovenia
15:50 – 16:05	ORGANYLPENTAFLUOROPHOSPHATE IONS
Oral	Jan-Hendrik Schröder , Bielefeld University, Germany
16:05 – 16:20	AUTOCATALYTIC DEGRADATION OF THE EXTREMELY POTENT GREENHOUSE GAS SF₆ IN BASIC ALCOHOLIC SOLUTION

Oral **Alexander Sietmann**, University of Innsbruck, Austria

16:20 – 16:35 **COPPER(I) COMPLEXES WITH WEAKLY BASIC LIGANDS: EXPLORING CU(I) INTERACTIONS WITH DINITROGEN AND FLUORINATED ARENES**

Oral **Julie Willrett**, University of Freiburg, Germany

PARALLEL SESSION II – ORGANOMETALLIC CHEMISTRY

Room: 3A

Chair: Jean-François Paquin, Université Laval, Canada

14:30 – 14:50 **PREPARATION AND STUDIES OF FLUORINATED LIGANDS AND THEIR METAL COMPLEXES (PT, PD, ZN, ETC.): FROM CATALYSIS TO THE NON-COVALENT BOND-INDUCED C-H AND C-C BOND CHANGES**

IL **Norman Lu**, Institute of Organic and Polymeric Materials, National Taipei University of Technology, Taiwan

14:50 – 15:10 **NOVEL CU^{III}CF₃ COMPOUNDS RELEVANT TO C–C AND C–HETEROATOM BOND FORMATION**

IL **Noel Nebra**, Laboratoire Hétérochimie Fondamentale et Appliquée (LHFA), CNRS - Université Toulouse III, France

15:10 – 15:30 **USING ORTHOCARBORANE AS A REPLACEMENT FOR THE ARYL GROUP TO GREATLY INCREASE THE OXIDIZING POWER OF "ARIF₂" AND "ARI(OT_F)₂"**

IL **Jason L. Dutton**, La Trobe University, Australia

15:30 – 15:45 **ENHANCING PD(IV) STABILITY: TRIFLUOROMETHYL ORGANOPALLADIUM COMPLEXES**

Oral **Juan Pueyo**, Instituto de Síntesis Química y Catálisis Homogénea (ISQCH), Spain

15:45 – 16:00 **INVESTIGATION OF CAAC STABILIZED NIOBIUM AND TANTALUM PENTAFLUORIDES**

Oral **Evelin Gruden**, Jožef Stefan Institute, Slovenia

16:00 – 16:15 **HOMOLEPTIC PLATINUM(IV)–CF₃ AND –OT_F COMPLEXES AS POTENTIAL PRECURSORS FOR PLATINUM SPECIES IN HIGHER OXIDATION STATES**

Oral **Niklas Limberg**, Freie Universität Berlin, Germany

Monday

PARALLEL SESSION II – CONTAMINANTS OF EMERGING CONCERN & FLUOROUS TECHNOLOGY SPONSORED BY LIFE4F-GASES

Room: 3B

Chair: Mark Shiflett, Wonderful Institute for Sustainable Engineering, University of Kansas, USA

14:30 – 15:00	DEVELOPMENT AND SCALE-UP OF THIN FILM POLYMER MEMBRANES FOR THE SEPARATION AND RECYCLING OF FLUORINATED REFRIGERANTS
IL	Gabriel Zarca , Universidad de Cantabria, Spain
15:00 – 15:15	CAPTURE AND SEPARATION OF FLUORINATED GASES WITH HIGH GLOBAL WARMING POTENTIAL
Oral	Julio E. Sosa , NOVA University Lisbon, Portugal
15:15 – 15:30	AN INNOVATIVE HYBRID MEMBRANE-ADSORPTION (HAMSYS) TECHNOLOGY FOR THE SELECTIVE RECOVERY OF F-GASES FROM DEPLETED REFRIGERANT BLENDS
Oral	Javier Pinedo Alonso , Apria, Spain
15:30 – 15:45	LIFE-4-FGASES: DISSEMINATION AND COMMUNICATION ACTIVITIES
Oral	Rosa Monforte , ERP, Portugal
15:45 – 16:00	AN INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGY FOR THE SELECTIVE RECOVERY OF F-GASES FROM DEPLETED REFRIGERANT BLENDS
Oral	Vanessa Gouveia , Ambigroup, Portugal

PARALLEL SESSION III – ORGANIC CHEMISTRY

Room: Auditorium II

Chair: David O'Hagan, University of St Andrews, UK

17:00 – 17:20	EXPANDING SF₅ CHEMISTRY
IL	Dominique Cahard , CNRS, France
17:20 – 17:40	COLLECTION OF QUALITY-EVALUATED PKA VALUES IN POLAR APROTIC SOLVENTS
IL	Ivo Leito , University of Tartu, Estonia
17:40 – 17:55	LIQUID-CRYSTALLINE PROPERTIES INDUCED BY INCORPORATING FLUORINES INTO D-Π-A TOLANE CONTAINING DECYLENEOXY CHAINS TERMINATED WITH IMIDAZOLIUM SALTS
Oral	Shigeyuki Yamada , Kyoto Institute of Technology, Japan
17:55 – 18:10	SIMPLE AND EFFICIENT APPROACH TO SULFONYL FLUORIDES
Oral	Masaaki Omote , Setsunan University, Japan

Monday

PARALLEL SESSION III – MATERIALS & FLUOROUS TECHNOLOGY

Room: 3A

Chair: Jean-Marc Vincent, University of Bordeaux - CNRS, France

17:00 – 17:20	KEY ASPECTS IN CORROSION OF SUPERALLOYS IN MOLTEN FLUORIDE SALTS
IL	Miroslav Boča , Institute of Inorganic Chemistry, Slovak Academy of Sciences, Slovakia
17:20 – 17:40	LOW-ENERGY ELECTRON INTERACTIONS WITH F-GASES REFRIGERANTS
IL	Filipe Ferreira da Silva , Universidade NOVA de Lisboa, Portugal
17:40 – 17:55	CONTROLLED SYNTHESIS AND PROPERTIES OF POLYVINYLIDENE FLUORIDE BASED METAL-FLUORIDE SURFACE TREATMENTS FOR HIGH-NICKEL NCM CATHODES
Oral	Chunjoong Kim , Chungnam National University, Korea
17:55 – 18:10	NEW FLUORINATION METHODS OF MOLYBDENUM DISULFIDE (MOS₂) FOR ENHANCED H₂ PRODUCTION PERFORMANCES
Oral	Pierre Bonnet , Université Clermont Auvergne, France
18:10 – 18:25	FLUORINATED SOFT-MATTER – COMPARTMENTALIZED MICELLES, HEMIMICELLES, MESOPHASES, MICROEMULSIONS AND MORE
Oral	Eduardo J. M. Filipe , Universidade de Lisboa, Portugal

PARALLEL SESSION III – CONTAMINANTS OF EMERGING CONCERN SPONSORED BY ALERT-PFAS

Room: 3B

Chair: Gabriel Zarca, Universidad de Cantabria, Spain

17:00 – 17:20	FUNCTIONAL MATERIAL FOR PFAS REMOVAL
IL	Mona Semsarilar , CNRS-European Institute of Membranes (IEM), France
17:20 – 17:40	HOW CAN PFAS BE PHOTOCHEMICALLY ELIMINATED FROM AQUATIC COMPARTMENTS?
IL	Gilles Mailhot , Institut de Chimie de Clermont-Ferrand, CNRS/Université Clermont Auvergne, France
17:40 – 18:00	FLUORINATED METHANE DERIVATIVES HYDRATES: A MOLECULAR SIMULATION STUDY
IL	Manuel M. Piñeiro , Universidade de Vigo, Spain
18:00 – 18:10	ALERT-PFAS SOLUTIONS - DIGITAL TOOL FOR MODELLING PFAS RISK IN NATURAL ENVIRONMENTS
Oral	Albert Serra Compte , Cetaqua, Spain
18:10 – 18:20	MONITORING OF PFAS HOTSPOTS AND SURFACE WATER TREATMENT SOLUTIONS IN NATURAL AREAS
Oral	Joana C. Bastos , NOVA University Lisbon, Portugal
18:20 – 18:30	TRANSNATIONAL STRATEGY FOR THE DETECTION OF PFAS UNDER ALERT-PFAS PROJECT
Oral	Catarina Novo , Instituto de Telecomunicações, Portugal

Monday

Tuesday, August 5th, 2025

PLENARY SESSION - VERONIQUE GOUVERNEUR

Room: Auditorium II

Chair: Norio Shibata, Nagoya Institute of Technology, Japan

09:00 – 10:00 **RETHINKING FLUORINE CHEMISTRY WITH GLOBAL CHALLENGES IN MIND**
PL **Veronique Gouverneur**, University of Oxford, UK

KEYNOTE SESSION - BEATE KOKSCH

Room: Auditorium II

Chair: Veronique Gouverneur, University of Oxford, UK

10:00 – 10:45 **FLUROPEPTIDES AS BIODEGRADABLE BIOPOLYMERS**
KN **Beate Kokschi**, Freie University of Berlin, Germany

PUBLIC DISCUSSION ABOUT PFAS

Room: Auditorium II

Moderator: Rita Santos, Journalist in Biosfera, Farol de Ideias, Portugal

11:15 – 12:15 **ROUNDTABLE 1: POLICY RECOMMENDATIONS FOR CONTAMINANTS OF EMERGING CONCERN**
Rolf-Jan Hoeve, DG ENVI, European Commission (TBC)
Veronique Gouverneur, University of Oxford, UK
Luis Simas, ERSAR, Portugal
Mark Shiflett, University of Kansas, USA
Romain Gandre, Veolia, France
Ronald Bock, AGC, UK
Vanessa Gouveia, Ambigroup, Portugal

Room: Auditorium II

Moderator: Rita Santos, Journalist in Biosfera, Farol de Ideias, Portugal

12:30 – 13:30 **ROUNDTABLE 2: SUSTAINABLE AND SAFE PFAS FOR HEALTH AND THE ENVIRONMENT**
Dexi Weng, Dexyan Global, USA Comeall Technology, China/USA
Nebojša Ilić, PFASuiki GmbH, Germany
Susana Fonseca, ZERO, Portugal
Marie-Pierre Krafft, University of Strasbourg, France
Lourdes F. Vega, Khalifa University, UAE
Bruno Ameduri, Institute Charles Gerhardt Montpellier, France
Beate Kokschi, Freie University of Berlin, Germany

Tuesday

SESSIONS ON PFAS AND EUROPEAN PROJECT ACTIVITIES

Please check all the information here: [Sessions on PFAS and European Project Activities](#)

Register here: <https://forms.office.com/e/7p5cYjHEAG>

FUNDING OPPORTUNITIES

Room: 3A

Moderator: Tamara Rodriguez, FEUGA, Spain

14:30 – 16:00 **EUROPEAN FUNDING OPPORTUNITIES**

Bernd Decker – Head of Sector, CINEA, European Commission

Vanda Pereira from APA (Portuguese Environment Agency) – Responsible for the LIFE Programme in Portugal

Ana Sutcliffe from ANI (National Innovation Agency) – Responsible for the Horizon Europe calls in Portugal

Raquel Rocha from AD&C (Agency for Development and Cohesion) – Responsible for the Interreg calls in Portugal

16:00 – 17:30 **EUROPEAN RESEARCH NETWORKING FORUM**

OPEN FUN HALL

Room: Pavilion 3 Main Hall

14:30 – 18:30 **FUN HALL – INNOVATION, LEARNING AND FUN**

Reading and Discovery Area

Interactive Games

Environmental Trivia

European Project Poster Exhibition

Cinema Room

'Aquaville' Game – Protect your City!

Tuesday

Wednesday, August 6th, 2025

PLENARY SESSION - DEXI WENG

Room: Auditorium II

Chair: Pierangelo Metrangolo, Politecnico di Milano, Italy

09:00 – 10:00 **CALCIUM FLUORIDE (FLUORSPAR) TO PERFLUOROORGANIC MATERIALS TO DATA OPTICALIZATION**

PL **Dexi Weng**, Dexyan Global, USA Comeall Technology, China/USA

KEYNOTE SESSION - MATTHEW HOPKINSON

Room: Auditorium II

Chair: Petr Beier, Institute of Organic Chemistry and Biochemistry, Czech Republic

10:00 – 10:45 **NOVEL METHODS FOR INSTALLING EMERGING FLUORINATED MOTIFS**

KN **Matthew N. Hopkinson**, Newcastle University, UK

PARALLEL SESSION IV – ORGANIC CHEMISTRY

Room: Auditorium II

Chair: Mark Crimmin, Imperial College London, UK

11:15 – 11:35 **EXPANDING THE TOOLBOX OF FLUORINATED MOTIFS: SELECTIVE STRATEGIES FOR FLUOROALKYLATION AND PFAS ALTERNATIVES**

IL **Frédéric R. Leroux**, University of Strasbourg, France

11:35 – 11:55 **A CONVENIENT OXIDATIVE FLUORINATION PROCEDURE TO FORM HYPERVALENT IODINE(V) FLUORIDES**

IL **Alison M. Stuart**, University of Leicester, UK

11:55 – 12:15 **TRANSITION METAL-CATALYZED DEFLUORINATIVE FUNCTIONALIZATION OF FLUORINATED AND PERFLUOROALKYLATED ALKENES**

IL **Gavin Chit Tsui**, The Chinese University of Hong Kong, China

12:15 – 12:30 **CAPITALIZING ON OXIME REARRANGEMENT CHEMISTRY FOR THE SYNTHESIS OF UNIQUE FLUORINE-CONTAINING MOTIFS**

Oral **Patrick R. Melvin**, Bryn Mawr College, USA

12:30 – 12:45 **ORGANIC MOLECULE AGGREGATION AND C-H BOND CLEAVAGE IN POLAR FLUORINATED ARENES**

Oral **Tianfei Liu**, Nankai University, China

12:45 – 13:00 **EXPLORATION OF NOVEL N-DIFLUOROMETHYL MOTIFS**

Oral **Gina Wycich**, RWTH Aachen University, Germany

13:00 – 13:15 **SYNTHESIS OF N-TRIFLUOROETHYL AND N-DIFLUOROETHYL AZAPEPTIDES AND AZAPEPTOIDS**

Oral **Dimitra Kyrko**, Université Paris Saclay, France

13:15 – 13:30 **THE ELECTROSTATIC NATURE OF HYDROGEN BONDING INTERACTIONS BETWEEN RCH₂F AND RCHF₂ MOTIFS**

Oral **Bruno A. Piscelli**, University of Campinas, Brazil

Wednesday

PARALLEL SESSION IV – FLUOROUS TECHNOLOGY & MATERIALS

Room: 3A

Chair: Kazuhiko Matsumoto, Kyoto University, Japan

11:15 – 11:35	EXPLORING THE FLAMMABILITY LIMITS OF FLUORINATED REFRIGERANT MIXTURES USING ARTIFICIAL NEURAL NETWORKS AND MOLECULAR DESCRIPTORS
IL	Fèlix Llovell , Universitat Rovira i Virgili, Spain
11:35 – 11:55	A_G(II)-BASED MAGNETIC PRECURSORS OF NOVEL SUPERCONDUCTORS
IL	Wojciech Grochala , University Warsaw, Poland
11:55 – 12:15	INTERFACIAL MOLECULAR ENGINEERING FOR FUNCTIONAL MATERIALS: NEW DESIGN PRINCIPLE FOR MATERIALS WITH PERMEABLE PROPERTIES
IL	Yoshimitsu Itoh , The University of Tokyo, Japan
12:15 – 12:35	EXPLORING SUPRAMOLECULAR CHEMISTRY AND PHOTOREDOX CATALYSIS WITH PFASS AND IN PFASS
IL	Jean-Marc Vincent , University of Bordeaux, France
12:35 – 12:50	PERFLUOROPOLYETHER-FUNCTIONALIZED CARBON-BASED MATERIALS AND THEIR APPLICATIONS IN ENERGY DEVICES
Oral	Maurizio Sansotera , Politecnico di Milano, Italy
12:50 – 13:05	LEVERAGING MOLECULAR THERMODYNAMICS AND MACHINE LEARNING FOR THE RATIONAL DESIGN OF ALTERNATIVE REFRIGERANT BLENDS
Oral	Ismail I. I. Alkhatib , Khalifa University, United Arab Emirates
13:05 – 13:20	COMPUTATIONAL MODELLING OF THE GLOBAL WARMING POTENTIAL CLIMATE METRIC ACROSS FLUORINATED MOLECULES
Oral	Luís P. Viegas , Universidade de Coimbra, Portugal
13:20 – 13:35	CHIRAL FLUOROALKYLIMINES IN ASYMMETRIC SYNTHESIS: ADVANCES AND APPLICATIONS
Oral	Yuliya Rassukana , National Academy of Sciences of Ukraine, Ukraine

PARALLEL SESSION IV – CONTAMINANTS OF EMERGING CONCERN

Room: 3B

Chair: Valentina Dichiarante, Politecnico di Milano, Italy

11:15 – 11:35	WHAT DO WE KNOW ABOUT PER- OR POLYFLUOROALKYL SUBSTANCES (PFASS)? ISSUES, CHALLENGES, REGULATIONS AND POSSIBLE ALTERNATIVES
IL	Bruno Ameduri , Institut Charles Gerhardt, France
11:35 – 11:55	FIREFIGHTERS' OCCUPATIONAL EXPOSURE TO PER- AND POLYFLUOROALKYL SUBSTANCES
IL	Marta Oliveira , Instituto Superior de Engenharia do Porto, Portugal
11:55 – 12:15	BREAKING THE CHAINS OF PFAS WITH ELECTROCHEMICAL OXIDATION – THE SUIKI BOTTOM-UP APPROACH
IL	Nebojša Ilić , PFASuiki GmbH, Germany
12:15 – 12:30	PFAS DEGRADATION DURING HAZARDOUS WASTE INCINERATION: A PILOT-SCALE STUDY WITH COMPREHENSIVE ANALYTICAL APPROACH
Oral	Muckensturm Gaël , Veolia Research and Innovation, France

12:30 – 12:45	PFAS REMOVAL FROM LANDFILL LEACHATES WITH AN ELECTROCHEMICALLY ASSISTED NANOFILTRATION MEMBRANE
Oral	Ane Urtiaga , University of Cantabria, Spain
12:45 – 13:00	COMPARISON OF PFAS CONTAMINATION BETWEEN TWO EUROPEAN AND ASIAN RIVERS
Oral	Khanh Vu , Aix-Marseille University, France
13:00 – 13:15	PFAS AND WATER RESOURCES: HOW TO DETERMINE THE BEST TREATMENT SOLUTION?
Oral	Romain Gandré , Veolia, France
13:15 – 13:30	REMOVAL OF PFAS FROM WATER BY ADSORPTION: RECENT PROGRESS AND FUTURE PERSPECTIVES
Oral	Daniel Dianchen Gang , University of Louisiana at Lafayette, USA

PARALLEL SESSION V – ORGANIC & ORGANOMETALLIC CHEMISTRY

Room: Auditorium II

Chair: Jason Dutton, La Trobe University, Australia

14:30 – 14:50	SELECTIVE FLUORINATED DEELECTRONATORS AND ORGANOMETALLIC METAL-DIMERS: A REACTIVE COUPLE TO ACCESS UNKNOWN CATIONS...
IL	Ingo Krossing , University of Freiburg, Germany
14:50 – 15:10	DEHYDROFLUORINATION OF LEGACY REFRIGERANTS AT GROUP 9 METAL PINNACLES COMPLEXES
IL	David A. Vicic , Lehigh University, USA
15:10 – 15:30	SYNTHETIC REACTIONS OF ISOLATED TRIFLUOROMETHYL ISOBENZOFURANS
IL	Hideki Amii , Gunma University, Japan
15:30 – 15:45	REVERSED ELECTROSTATIC DESIGN FOR SELECTIVE RECOGNITION OF BTX VIA π-HOLE$\cdots\pi$ INTERACTIONS BY A TETRAOXA[2]PERFLUOROARENE[2]TRIAZINE HOST
Oral	Akiko Hori , Shibaura Institute of Technology, Japan
15:45 – 16:00	[(TRIISOPROPYLSILYL)ACETYLENE]SULFUR PENTAFLUORIDE – A VALUABLE REAGENT FOR ACCESSING UNPRECEDENTED CLASSES OF SF₅-CONTAINING BUILDING BLOCKS
Oral	David Rombach , University of Zurich, Switzerland
16:00 – 16:15	UNUSUAL ROLE OF HEXAFLUOROISOPROPANOL IN REDOX-ACTIVATED CYCLOADDITIONS
Oral	Michał J. Jadwiszczak , University of Warsaw, Poland
16:15 – 16:30	NEW ACCESS ROUTES TOWARD THIOCARBAMOYL FLUORIDES AND TRIFLUOROMETHANESULFENAMIDES USING AN EASY-TO-USE AND SHELF-STABLE CF₃S-REAGENT
Oral	Clément Delobel , Institute of chemistry and biochemistry (ICBMS), France
16:30 – 16:45	A NEW SULFOXIMINE SCAFFOLD FOR THE GENERATION OF DIVERSE FLUORINATED RADICALS IN PHOTOREDOX CATALYSIS
Oral	Gabriel Goujon , Institut Lavoisier de Versailles - UVSQ, France
16:45 – 17:00	STEREOSELECTIVE SYNTHESIS OF (2S,4S)-5,5,5,5',5'-PENTAFLUOROLEUCINE AND (2S,4R)-5,5,5-TRIFLUOROLEUCINE
Oral	Sandeep Mummadi , European Institute of Chemistry and Biology (IECB), France

Wednesday

17:00 – 17:15 **ENANTIOSELECTIVE CONSTRUCTION OF A FLUORINATED TERTIARY CARBON USING PRIMARY AMINE CATALYSTS**

Oral **Satoru Arimitsu**, University of the Ryukyus, Japan

PARALLEL SESSION V – ORGANIC CHEMISTRY

Room: 3A

Chair: Thierry Billard, CNRS - University of Lyon, France

14:30 – 14:50 **UPGRADING THE HALOGEN BOND DONOR ABILITY OF ORGANIC FLUOROARENES**

IL **Giuseppe Resnati**, Politecnico di Milano, Italy

14:50 – 15:10 **CATALYST FREE O-ARYLATION REACTIONS OF FLUOROBENZENES**

IL **Frederik Diness**, Roskilde University, Denmark

15:10 – 15:25 **ACTIVATION OF AROMATIC CARBON–FLUORINE BONDS: COUPLING REACTION OF FLUOROBENZOFURANS**

Oral **Junji Ichikawa**, Sagami Chemical Research Institute, Japan

15:25 – 15:40 **POLYFLUOROALKOXYLATION OF DIARYLIODONIUM SALTS VIA ELIMINATIVE LIGAND COUPLING USING POLYFLUOROALKOXY BORATE SALTS**

Oral **Kotaro Kikushima**, Ritsumeikan University, Japan

15:40 – 15:55 **SELECTIVE C(SP³)-F BOND FUNCTIONALIZATION OF TRIFLUOROMETHYL ARENES UTILIZING EDA COMPLEX**

Oral **Takahiko Akiyama**, Gakushuin University, Japan

15:55 – 16:10 **FUNCTIONAL GROUP TRANSFORMATION AT C5 POSITION OF FLUORINATED ISOXAZOLINES VIA C-F BOND CLEAVAGE**

Oral **Kazuyuki Sato**, Setsunan University, Japan

16:10 – 16:25 **PHOTOACID-INDUCED ADDITION OF KETENE Silyl ACETALS TO FLUORINATED LSOCOUMARINS AND DEFLUORINATIVE RING REARRANGEMENT OF THE ADDUCTS**

Oral **Hikaru Yanai**, Tokyo University of Pharmacy and Life Sciences, Japan

Wednesday

PARALLEL SESSION V – INORGANIC CHEMISTRY, COMPUTATIONAL CHEMISTRY & BIOORGANIC & MEDICINAL CHEMISTRY

Room: 3B

Chair: Rodrigo Cormanich, Universidade Estadual de Campinas, Brazil

14:30 – 14:50	BIS(TRIFLUOROMETHYL)AMINES – SYNTHESIS & PROPERTIES
IL	Maik Finze , University of Wurzburg, Germany
14:50 – 15:10	WHY FINDING THE PERFECT SUSTAINABLE REFRIGERANT IS HARDER THAN YOU THINK
IL	Lourdes F. Vega , Khalifa University of Science and Technology, United Arab Emirates
15:10 – 15:25	THE FLUORINASE – PAST, PRESENT AND FUTURE
Oral	Phillip T. Lowe , University of St Andrews, UK
15:25 – 15:40	NEW AVENUES IN ORGANOXENON CHEMISTRY
Oral	Alberto Pérez-Bitrián , Humboldt-Universität zu Berlin, Germany
15:40 – 15:55	PENTAFLUOROPHOSPHATES AS BIOMIMETICS OF PHOSHOPEPTIDES AND PHOSPHOPROTEINS
Oral	Anna Magdalena Ambros , Freie Universität Berlin, Germany
15:55 – 16:10	SYNTHESIS AND REACTIVITY OF FLUORINATED ALKYL HALONIUM IONS
Oral	Lukas Fischer , Freie Universität Berlin, Germany
16:10 – 16:25	PHOSPHONATE ANALOGUES OF FLUOROPHENYLGLYCINES AS POTENTIAL INHIBITORS OF HUMAN UROKINASE PLASMINOGEN ACTIVATOR: SYNTHESIS, STRUCTURE AND ANTICANCER ACTIVITY
Oral	Donata Pluskota-Karwatka , Adam Mickiewicz University in Poznań, Poland
16:25 – 16:40	FLUORINATION OF ROTAXANES FOR SENSITIVE 19F MR-FLUORESCENCE DUAL IMAGING
Oral	Zhong Xing Jiang , Chinese Academy of Sciences, China
16:40 – 16:55	PHOSPHONIUM SF₅⁻ SALTS DERIVED FROM SF₆ AS OXIDATIVE FLUORINATION AND DEOXYFLUORINATION AGENTS
Oral	Kim Schramke , Department of General, Inorganic and Theoretical Chemistry, Austria

Wednesday

Wednesday

Thursday, August 7th, 2025

PLENARY SESSION - FENG-LING QING

Room: Auditorium II

Chair: Matthew Hopkinson, Newcastle University, UK

09:00 – 10:00 **SYNTHESIS AND APPLICATION OF PENTAFLUOROSULFANYL (SF₅)-CONTAINING REAGENTS**

PL **Feng-Ling Qing**, Shanghai Institute of Organic Chemistry, China

KEYNOTE SESSION - BERTHOLD HOGE

Room: Auditorium II

Chair: Joseph Thrasher, Clemson University, USA

10:00 – 10:45 **PERFLUOROORGANYL GALLIUM AND INDIUM CHEMISTRY: THE FIRST MAIN GROUP ELEMENT LEWIS ACID THIONYL CHLORIDE ADDUCT AND ITS CHEMISTRY**

KN **Berthold Hoge**, Bielefeld University, Germany

PARALLEL SESSION VI – ORGANIC & ORGANOMETALLIC CHEMISTRY

Room: Auditorium II

Chair: David Vacic, Lehigh University, USA

11:15 – 11:35 **RHODIUM-MEDIATED C-H AND C-F BOND ACTIVATION TO ACCESS FLUORINATED ALKENE DERIVATIVES**

IL **Thomas Braun**, Humboldt University Berlin, Germany

11:35 – 11:55 **MECHANISTIC INSIGHT ON COPPER-MEDIATED TRIFLUOROMETHYLATION**

IL **Qilong Shen**, Shanghai Institute of Organic Chemistry, China

11:55 – 12:15 **ORGANOFLUORINE TRANSITION METAL CHEMISTRY MEETS CARBENE CHEMISTRY**

IL **Miguel Baya**, Universidad de Zaragoza, Spain

12:15 – 12:30 **ORGANOMETALLIC CHEMISTRY OF THE PERFLUORINATED CP* LIGAND [C₅(CF₃)₅]⁻**

Oral **Moritz Malischewski**, Freie Universität Berlin, Germany

12:30 – 12:45 **MIGRATORY ALLYLIC C-F BOND FUNCTIONALIZATION**

Oral **Jean-Denys Hamel**, University of Lethbridge, Canada

12:45 – 13:00 **SYNTHETIC APPROACH TO CF₃-ALKENYL DERIVATIVES OF AMINO ACIDS**

Oral **Katarzyna Koroniak-Szejn**, Adam Mickiewicz University, Poland

Thursday

PARALLEL SESSION VI – CONTAMINANTS OF EMERGING CONCERN & MATERIALS & ORGANIC CHEMISTRY

Room: 3A

Chair: Cormac Murphy, University College Dublin, Ireland

11:15 – 11:35	SUPRAMOLECULAR ARCHITECTURES AND HYDROGELS BASED ON FLUORINATED AMINO ACIDS
IL	Valentina Dichiarante , Politecnico di Milano, Italy
11:35 – 11:50	COMPLETE MINERALIZATION OF LITHIUM BIS(PENTAFLUOROETHANE-SULFONYL)IMIDE AND RELATED ELECTROLYTE FLUORO CHEMICALS USING SUPERHEATED WATER
Oral	Hisao Hori , Kanagawa University, Japan
11:50 – 12:05	OCCURRENCE, DISTRIBUTION AND FATE OF FLUORINE DURING PHOSPHATE ORE PROCESSING
Oral	Kamal Benali , Fluoralpha, Morocco
12:05 – 12:20	ORGANOCATALYZED SYNTHESIS AND DEPOLYMERIZATION OF FLUORINATED POLYSILOXANES, A ROUTE TO THEIR CHEMICAL RECYCLING
Oral	Vincent Ladmiral , National Centre for Scientific Research (CNRS), France
12:20 – 12:35	INNOVATIVE BIFUNCTIONAL SILOXANE AND THEIR POTENTIAL APPLICATION
Oral	Joanna Karasiewicz , Adam Mickiewicz University Poznan, Poland
12:35 – 12:50	IMPACTING HIGH PRESSURE STRUCTURAL TRANSITION OF ALKALI METAL HEXAFLUORIDES
Oral	Kevin Lemoine , Université Clermont Auvergne, France
12:50 – 13:05	SYNTHESIS OF α-FLUOROALKYLATED PYRIDINES AND PYRIMIDINES VIA DIRECT FLUORINATION WITH NFSI
Oral	Petro Onys'ko , National Academy of Sciences of Ukraine, Ukraine
13:05 – 13:20	AMINE-FUNCTIONALIZED FLUOROARENES FOR ENERGY AND ENVIRONMENTAL APPLICATIONS
Oral	Anastasios Stergiou , Politecnico di Milano, Italy
13:20 – 13:35	MANAGED AQUIFER RECHARGE: A NEW FRONTIER FOR ADDRESSING EMERGING CONTAMINANTS
Oral	Srdana Kolakovic , NOVA University Lisbon, Portugal

PARALLEL SESSION VI – ORGANIC CHEMISTRY

Room: 3B

Chair: Gavin Chit Tsui, The Chinese University of Hong Kong, China

11:15 – 11:35	CHEMICAL RECYCLING OF FLUOROCARBONS BY TRANSFER FLUORINATION
IL	Mark R. Crimmin , Imperial College London, UK
11:35 – 11:55	THE ROLE OF ELECTROSTATIC NON-CONVENTIONAL HYDROGEN BONDING INTERACTIONS IN ORGANOFUORINE COMPOUNDS
IL	Rodrigo A. Cormanich , Universidade Estadual de Campinas, Brazil

Thursday

11:55 – 12:15	RECENT ADVANCES IN THE SYNTHESIS OF PENTAFLUOROSULFANYLATED MOLECULES
IL	Jean-François Paquin , Université Laval, Canada
12:15 – 12:35	EXPERIMENTAL AND THEORETICAL STUDY OF DIFLUOROBENZIMIDAZOLES
IL	Jaroslav Kvičala , University of Chemistry and Technology, Czechia
12:35 – 12:50	SHELF-STABLE REAGENT FOR RADICAL PENTAFLUOROSULFANYLATION
Oral	Yi Yang , Université Claude Bernard Lyon1, France
12:50 – 13:05	TETRAFLUOROPYRIDYL GROUPS; APPLICATIONS IN MOLECULAR FUNCTIONALISATION
Oral	William D. G. Brittain , Durham University, UK
13:05 – 13:20	THIONYL FLUORIDE AS A SULFUR(IV) S₀FE_x HUB FOR THE EFFICIENT SYNTHESIS OF SULFINAMIDES AND SULFINATE ESTERS
Oral	William P. Chappell , The University of British Columbia, Canada

PARALLEL SESSION VII – INORGANIC CHEMISTRY

Room: Auditorium II

Chair: Miroslav Boča, Institute of Inorganic Chemistry, Slovak Academy of Sciences, Slovakia

14:30 – 14:50	EXPLORING XENON DIFLUORIDE COORDINATION COMPOUNDS: FROM INITIAL DISCOVERIES TO NOVEL SO₃F⁻ ANION
IL	Gašper Tavčar , Jožef Stefan Institute, Slovenia
14:50 – 15:10	MANIPULATING F...F INTERACTIONS FOR METAL EXTRACTIONS
IL	Robert J. Baker , University of Dublin, Trinity College, Ireland
15:10 – 15:25	FLUORINATION BY SOLID-GAS REACTION OF HIGH-PERFORMANCE COMPOUNDS FOR RECHARGEABLE BATTERIES
Oral	Saida Moumen , Clermont-Auvergne University, France
15:25 – 15:40	SIMPLE ACCESS TO A SERIES OF HIGHER SUBSTITUTED PENTAFLUOROORTHOTELLURATE-BASED SILANES AND GERMANES
Oral	Friederike Oesten , Freie Universität Berlin, Germany
15:40 – 15:55	SYNTHESIS AND REACTIVITY OF ZINC-FLUORIDE COORDINATION COMPLEXES
Oral	Aaranjah Vickneswaran , Imperial College London, UK
15:55 – 16:10	THE TRIFLUOROXYGENATE ANION [OF₃]⁻: SPECTROSCOPIC EVIDENCE FOR A BINARY, HYPERVALENT OXYGEN SPECIES
Oral	Deniz F. Meyer , Freie Universität Berlin, Germany
16:10 – 16:25	ELECTROCHEMICAL FLUORINATION – A VERSATILE TOOL FOR THE LARGE SCALE SYNTHESIS OF PARTIALLY FLUORINATED BUILDING BLOCKS
Oral	Tanja Knuplez , University of Würzburg, Germany
16:25 – 16:40	NITROSYL FLUORIDE (FNO) AND NITRYL FLUORIDE (FNO₂) AS FLUORINATING AGENTS FOR INORGANIC MATERIALS
Oral	Batiste Clavier , Université Clermont Auvergne, France

Thursday

PARALLEL SESSION VII – ORGANIC CHEMISTRY

Room: 3A

Chair: Frédéric Leroux, University of Strasbourg - CNRS, France

14:30 – 14:50	AMINOPHOSPHONATES BEARING FLUORINE ATOMS AS INHIBITORS OF AMINOPEPTIDASES – SYNTHESIS AND PROPERTIES
IL	Henryk Koroniak , Adam Mickiewicz University, Poznań, Poland
14:50 – 15:10	NOVEL APPROACHES IN ASYMMETRIC CATALYTIC SYNTHESIS OF HALO-ORGANIC COMPOUNDS
IL	Mark Gandelman , Technion - Israel Institute of Technology, Israel
15:10 – 15:30	THE VALUE OF FLUORINE IN AGRICULTURAL CHEMISTRY
IL	Michael Rack , BASF SE, Germany
15:30 – 15:45	EFFECT OF AMINE DEPROTONATION ON S_uFE_x: SYNTHESIS OF SULFONAMIDES
Oral	Jan Dudziński , University of Warsaw, Poland
15:45 – 16:00	AN UNUSUAL REACTION OF FLUORINE SUBSTITUTION IN PENTAFLUOROiodo- AND PENTAFLUOROBROMOBENZENES BY AMINO SPECIES RUNNING AT AMBIENT CONDITIONS
Oral	Evgeny Goreshnik , Jožef Stefan Institute, Slovenia
16:00 – 16:15	CROSS-COUPLING REACTIONS USING MULTIHALOGENATED ALKENES SYNTHESIZED FROM HALOTHANE
Oral	Yukiko Karuo , Setsunan University, Japan
16:15 – 16:30	DEFLUORINATIVE SYNTHESIS OF MONOFLUOROALKENES VIA PHOTOREDOX C–C COUPLING OF α-AMINOALKYL RADICALS AND ALLYLIC DIFLUORIDES
Oral	Taylor Semeniuk , University of Lethbridge, Canada

PARALLEL SESSION VII – ORGANIC CHEMISTRY

Room: 3B

Chair: Frederik Diness, Roskilde University, Denmark

14:30 – 14:50	PERFLUORO-TERT-BUTY ANION: PREPARATION, STRUCTURE, AND REACTIVITY
IL	Jinbo Hu , Chinese Academy of Sciences, China
14:50 – 15:10	ON THE IMPORTANCE OF MICHAELIS–MENTEN KINETICS
IL	Rimantas Knizikevičius , Kaunas University of Technology, Lithuania
15:10 – 15:30	FROM TRIFLUOROMETHOXYLATION TO DIFLUOROPHOSGENE CHEMISTRY: A JOURNEY WITH 2,4-DINITRO-TRIFLUOROMETHOXYBENZENE (DNTFB)
IL	Thierry Billard , University of Lyon, France
15:30 – 15:45	LEWIS ACID-CATALYZED CARBOFLUORINATION VIA FLUORIDE RECYCLING
Oral	Christine M. Le , York University, Canada
15:45 – 16:00	REACTIONS OF HEXAFLUOROTHIOACETONE DIMER (HFTAD) WITH TERPENES
Oral	Viacheslav Petrov , Fluorinova LLC, USA

Thursday

16:00 – 16:15 **HF SHUTTLING FOR THE CHEMICAL RECYCLING OF FLUOROCARBONS**

Oral **Shannon E. S. Farley**, Imperial College London, UK

FLASH PRESENTATIONS

Room: Auditorium II

Chair: Maik Finze, University of Wurzburg, Germany

17:00 – 17:05 **ACTIVATION OF PERFLUORO(METHYL VINYL ETHER) AT Rh(I) PHOSPHINE COMPLEXES: METAL-CENTERED VERSUS PHOSPHINE MEDIATED DECARBONYLATION**

FP **Soodeh Mollasalehi**, Humboldt-Universität zu Berlin, Germany

17:05 – 17:10 **C–F BOND ACTIVATION OF FLUOROALKANES VIA GERMILIUM IONS CATALYSIS**

FP **Julie Borel**, Humboldt-Universität zu Berlin, Germany

17:10 – 17:15 **RESPIROMETRIC ANALYSIS FOR MONITORING THE MICROBIAL ACTIVITY DURING EXPOSURE TO PERFLUOROBUTANESULFONIC AND PERFLUOROHXANESULFONIC ACID**

FP **Natalija Petronijevic**, University of Belgrade, Serbia

17:15 – 17:20 **NOVEL HEXAFLUROSULFUR ACTIVATION UTILIZING AN ORGANIC PHOTOREDOX CATALYST**

FP **Max Flügge**, Karlsruhe Institute of Technology, Germany

17:20 – 17:25 **INVESTIGATING THE SITE-SPECIFIC IMPACT OF FLUORINE SUBSTITUTION ON AROMATIC INTERACTIONS IN A TRYPTOPHAN ZIPPER PEPTIDE**

FP **David Reiter**, Freie Universität Berlin, Germany

17:25 – 17:30 **DEVELOPMENT AND CHARACTERIZATION OF INNOVATIVE MATERIALS FOR PHOTOCATALYTIC DEGRADATION OF PERFLUOROCTANOIC ACID**

FP **Kristina Kasalica**, University of Belgrade, Serbia

17:30 – 17:35 **SEARCH FOR NOVEL SUPERCONDUCTORS IN A CHEMICAL CAPACITOR SETUP**

FP **Dawid Ciszewski**, University of Warsaw, Poland

17:35 – 17:40 **APPLICATION OF CF₃-NITRILE IMINES IN THE SYNTHESIS OF UNSYMMETRICAL N',N'-TRIFLUOROACETOHYDRAZIDES**

FP **Adrian Warcholiński**, University of Lodz, Poland

17:40 – 17:45 **DESULFURATIVE FLUORINATION OF ALKYL PHENYL SULFIDES**

FP **Brian Durkan**, Royal College of Surgeons, Ireland

17:45 – 17:50 **EXPANDING THE CHEMICAL SPACE OF PENTAFLUROSULFANYL-CONTAINING COMPOUNDS**

FP **Lujie Xu**, University of Zurich, Switzerland

17:50 – 17:55 **SEMI-CATALYTIC TRIFLUOROMETHYLATION USING TETRAKIS(TRIFLUOROMETHYL)COPPER**

FP **Petr Pospíšil**, Czech Academy of Sciences, Czechia

17:55 – 18:00 **INVESTIGATION OF DICATIONIC IONIC LIQUIDS WITH DIFLUOROPHOSPHATE ANION**

FP **Kentaro Kamada**, Kyoto University, Japan

Thursday

18:00 – 18:05	FROM TRIFLUOROMETHYL TO PENTAFLUOROETHYL: NEW APPROACHES IN GOLD(III) COMPLEXES STABILIZATION
FP	Alba de Toro , Universidad de Zaragoza CSIC, Spain
18:05 – 18:10	THE BIOINORGANIC IMPACT OF FLUORINE STUDIED BY VIBRATIONAL SPECTROSCOPY
FP	Soumyamoy Pathak , Freie University Berlin, Germany
18:10 – 18:15	FUNCTIONALIZATION OF NANODIAMONDS WITH PERFLUOROPOLYETHER PEROXIDE VIA A FACILE THERMOCHEMICAL PROCESS
FP	Davide Ceriotti , Politecnico di Milano, Italy

Thursday

Friday, August 8th, 2025

PLENARY SESSION - FLORIAN KRAUS

Room: Auditorium II

Chair: Berthold Hoge, Bielefeld University, Germany

09:00 – 10:00 **OXIDATION OF HALOGEN PENTAFLUORIDES AND N₂**

PL **Florian Kraus**, Philipps-Universität Marburg, Germany

KEYNOTE SESSION - CORMAC MURPHY

Room: Auditorium II

Chair: Marie-Pierre Krafft, Institut Charles Sadron (UPR 22), University of Strasbourg, France

10:00 – 10:45 **MICROBIAL ENZYMES THAT DEGRADE PFAS**

KN **Cormac D. Murphy**, University College Dublin, Ireland

KEYNOTE SESSION - KAZUHIKO MATSUMOTO

Room: Auditorium II

Chair: Michael Gerken, University of Lethbridge, Canada

11:15 – 12:00 **FLUORINE CHEMISTRY IN ENERGY APPLICATIONS**

KN **Kazuhiko Matsumoto**, Kyoto University, Japan

PLENARY SESSION - PETR BEIER

Room: Auditorium II

Chair: Henryk Koroniak, Adam Mickiewicz University, Poland

12:00 – 13:00 **FLUORINATED ORGANIC AZIDES IN SYNTHESIS AND BIOCONJUGATION**

PL **Petr Beier**, Institute of Organic Chemistry and Biochemistry, Czech Republic

CLOSING SESSION AND AWARDS

Room: Auditorium II

13:00 – 14:30 **CLOSING SESSION & AWARDS**

Ana B. Pereiro and João M. M. Araújo, NOVA FCT, Portugal

Presentations of the next ESFC (Czech Republic) and ISFC (France)

Award ceremony for the best posters

Closing words

Friday

Friday

Scientific Programme: Posters

Wednesday, August 6th, 2025: 17:30–19:30

Room: Pavilion 3

ORGANIC CHEMISTRY

P01 RADICAL PHOTOCHEMICAL DIFLUOROSULFOXIMINATION OF ALKENES AND PROPELLANES

Julien Paut, University of Paris-Saclay, France

P03 SYNTHESIS OF HFIP ESTERS VIA DEFLUORINATION OF AROMATIC TRIFLUOROMETHYL GROUPS

Shoki Hoshikawa, Setsunan University, Japan

P04 STRAIN-RELEASE-DRIVEN SYNTHESIS OF PERFLUOROSULFANYLATED FOUR-MEMBERED RINGS UNDER ENERGY TRANSFER PHOTOCATALYSIS

Lulu Han, Université Claude Bernard Lyon 1, France

P05 DECOMPOSITION OF PTFE BY THE VIBRATION MILL

Shiina Yasugami, Daikin Industries, LTD, Japan

P06 MECHANOCHEMICAL DIFLUOROMETHYLATION WITH HYPERVALENT IODINE REAGENTS

Vitalii Solomin, University of Rouen Normandy, France

P07 S_NAR REACTIONS OF PHENOL DERIVATIVES WITH FLUOROBENZENE

Feng Wang, Roskilde University, Denmark

P08 PYRIDINIUM-BASED FLUOROSULFONAMIDE REAGENTS ENABLED PHOTOREDOX-CATALYZED RADICAL FLUOROSULFONAMIDATION

Chao Sun, Nanjing University, China

P09 THE REACTIVITY OF TETRAFLUORO(TRIFLUOROMETHYL)- λ^6 -SULFANYL CHLORIDE (CF₃SF₄Cl) WITH SUBSTITUTED ALKYNES AND REACTIONS OF THE ADDUCTS FORMED

Elleanor van der Riet, University at Albany, USA

P10 THE INFLUENCE OF *N*-(2-(TETRAFLUORO(TRIFLUOROMETHYL)- λ^6 -SULFANYL) ETHYL)(*N*-CF₃SF₄-ETHYL) GROUPS ON PEPTIDE BOND FORMATION AND AMIDE BOND CONFORMATION.

Willow M. Desoucey, University at Albany, USA

P11 THE APPLICATION OF SULFUR HEXAFLUORIDE IN SYNTHETIC CHEMISTRY FOR PENTAFLUOROSULFANYLATION

Sven Klehenz, Karlsruhe Institute of Technology, Germany

P12 EXPANDING THE CHEMICAL SPACE OF PENTAFLUOROSULFANYL-CONTAINING COMPOUNDS

Lujie Xu, University of Zurich, Switzerland

P13 NOVEL HEXAFLUOROSULFUR ACTIVATION UTILIZING AN ORGANIC PHOTOREDOX CATALYST

Max Flügge, Karlsruhe Institute of Technology, Germany

P14	INVESTIGATING DNA BINDING OF ALL-<i>CIS</i>PENTAFLUOROCYCLOHEXANES USING FRET <i>George Kingsley-Moore</i> , University of St Andrews, UK
P15	PHOTO-CATALYTIC SYNTHESIS OF FLUORINATED SUPERACIDIC CARBON ACIDS <i>Rikuto Fujimoto</i> , Tokyo University of Pharmacy and Life Sciences, Japan
P16	SYNTHESIS AND PROPERTIES OF SELECTIVELY FLUORINATED <i>tert</i>-LEUCINE DERIVATIVES <i>Josephine M. Stewart</i> , University of St Andrews, UK
P17	UNLOCKING THE PENTAFLUROSULFANYLATION REACTIVITY OF SF₆ BY PHOTOREDOX CATALYSIS <i>David Rombach</i> , University of Zurich, Switzerland
P18	SYNTHESIS OF α,α-DIFLUORO-β-THIOCARBOXYLATES FOR A CYSTATIN-FREE CHEMICAL LIGATION <i>Atsushi Tarui</i> , Setsunan University, Japan
P19	ROOM TEMPERATURE IONIC LIQUIDS – ADVANCED REACTION MEDIA FOR ORGANIC SYNTHESSES WITH HIGHLY REACTIVE CHEMICALS – LET'S MAKE FLUORINATION SAFER <i>Nicolai V. Ignatyev</i> , Universität Würzburg, Germany
P20	APPLICATION OF CF₃-NITRILE IMINES IN THE SYNTHESIS OF UNSYMMETRICAL <i>N,N</i>-TRIFLUOROACETOHYDRAZIDES <i>Adrian Warcholiński</i> , University of Lodz, Poland
P21	SYNTHETIC STRATEGIES LEVERAGING FLUORIDE-ENABLED REACTIVITY AND SELECTIVITY <i>Christine M. Le</i> , York University, United Kingdom
P22	BICYCLO[1.1.1]PENTANES WITH FLUORO AND FLUOROALKYL SUBSTITUENTS: REDOX-ACTIVE ESTERS AND THEIR REACTIVITY <i>Stacie K. Nelson</i> , University of Lethbridge, Canada
P23	DEVELOPMENT OF PERFLUORO ALKOXYLATION REAGENTS AND SYNTHESIS OF PERFLUOROALKYL ETHERS <i>Moe Fujishiro (Hosokawa)</i> , Daikin Industries, LTD, Japan
P24	HIGHLY SELECTIVE SYNTHESIS OF REGIO- AND STEREOISOMERS OFFLUOROALKYLATED 1,3-ENYNS BY OPTIMAL USE OF CATALYST <i>Yuta Kabumoto</i> , Kyoto Institute of Technology, Japan
P25	STEREO- AND REGIOSELECTIVE VICINAL FLUOROSULFONYL-BORYLATION OF UNSATURATED HYDROCARBONS <i>Heyin Li</i> , Nanjing University, China
P26	DESULFURATIVE FLUORINATION OF ALKYL PHENYL SULFIDES <i>Brian Durkan</i> , Royal College of Surgeons, Ireland
P27	VISIBLE-LIGHT-MEDIATED TRIFLUOROMETHYLATION/RING CLOSURE SEQUENCES OF 2-VINYL PHENOLS: SYNTHESIS OF TRIFLUOROMETHYLATED 4<i>H</i>-CHROMENE DERIVATIVES <i>Dae Young Kim</i> , Soonchunhyang University, South Korea
P28	THE SYNTHESIS OF <i>N</i>-SUBSTITUTED HYDROXAMIC ACIDS VIA A PENTAFLUOROPYRIDINE MEDIATED PROCEDURE <i>Daniel E. Bonn</i> , Durham University, United Kingdom

P29 MILD C-F ACTIVATION OF PERFLUOROALKYL SUBSTANCES BY α -FLUORINE SUBSTITUTION OF PERFLUOROALKYL AZIDES WITH THIOLS

Olena Shaitanova, Academy of Sciences of the Czech Republic, Czechia

P82 USE OF CYCLIC SULFOXIMINES AS (DEUTERO)(FLUORO)METHYLATION REAGENTS

Gabriel Goujon, Institut Lavoisier de Versailles - UVSQ, France

P83 DIAMINOMETHYLATION OF FLUOROPYRIDINES

Aleksandr Kostyuk, Institute of Organic Chemistry, Ukraine

ORGANOMETALLIC CHEMISTRY

P30 BENZIMIDAZOLE-2-YLIDENE-SILVER(I) COMPLEXES BEARING THE 4-TRIFLUOROMETHOXY GROUP AS ORGANOFLUORINE COMPOUNDS: SYNTHESIS, CHARACTERIZATION, AND INHIBITORY PROPERTIES AGAINST SOME METABOLIC ENZYMES

Yetkin Gök, Inonu University, Turkey

P31 SYNTHESIS AND CHARACTERIZATION OF PD(II) METAL COMPLEXES DERIVED FROM N-HETEROCYCLIC CARBENES WITH FLUORINATED SUBSTITUENTS

Burcu Tezcan, Çukurova University, Turkey

P32 FROM TRIFLUOROMETHYL TO PENTAFLUOROETHYL: NEW APPROACHES IN GOLD(III) COMPLEXES STABILIZATION

Alba de Toro, Universidad de Zaragoza CSIC, Spain

P33 ACTIVATION OF PERFLUORO(METHYL VINYL ETHER) AT Rh(I) PHOSPHINE COMPLEXES: METAL-CENTERED VERSUS PHOSPHINE MEDIATED DECARBONYLATION

Soodeh Mollasalehi, Humboldt-Universität zu Berlin, Germany

P34 SEMI-CATALYTIC TRIFLUOROMETHYLATION USING TETRAKIS(TRIFLUOROMETHYL)COPPER

Petr Pospíšil, Czech Academy of Sciences, Czechia

P35 PENTAFLUOROETHYL STABILIZED α -SILYL CARBANIONS

Julia Landwehrmann, Universität Bielefeld, Germany

INORGANIC CHEMISTRY

P36 NOVEL READILY AVAILABLE LANTHANIDE-HALIDE COMPLEXES AS POTENTIAL PRECURSORS TO SINGLE MOLECULE MAGNETS

Magdalena Abramowicz, University of Warsaw, Poland

P37 HYDRODEFUORINATION WITH HETEROGENOUS ZIEGLER-NATTA CATALYSTS

Diego De Candidiis, Università degli Studi di Napoli Federico II, Italy

P38 SYNTHESIS OF FLUORINATED Zn(II) COORDINATION 2D SHEETS WITH ADAPTIVE PORE STRUCTURES FOR π -HOLE-INDUCED GUEST ENCAPSULATION

Akiko Hori, Shibaura Institute of Technology, Japan

P39 SYNTHESIS AND APPLICATION OF THE WEAKLY COORDINATING ANION [CHB₁₁F₁₁]⁻

Johanna Drolshagen, Universität Freiburg, Germany

P40 FROM STABLE HALOGENATED SUPERELECTROPHILIC TRITYLCATIONS TO CORRESPONDING LUMINESCENT TRITYLRADICALS AND THEIR PEROXIDES

Johanna Schlögl, Freie Universität Berlin, Germany

P41	CF₃OCH₂C(O)OH AND (CF₃)₂NCH₂C(O)OH – TWO PARTIALLY FLUORINATED ACIDS Sabine Lorenzen , University Würzburg, Germany
P42	BIS(PERFLUOROORGANYL)DISELANES AND -DITELLANES Kjell Simon Krauser , Universität Bielefeld, Germany
P43	FLUORIDE-ION DONOR PROPERTIES OF MoOF₄ AND WOF₄ Craig W. Sommer , University of Lethbridge, Canada
P44	NEW SYNTHETIC ROUTES FOR ARYLXENONIUM(II) SALTS AND STUDY OF THEIR LEWIS ACIDITY Pablo Cortés Soláns , Humboldt-Universität zu Berlin, Germany
P45	PLATINUM-CATALYSED HYDROFLUORINATION OF ALKYNES PROMOTED BY A FLUORIDE SHUTTLE Ouchan He , Humboldt-Universität zu Berlin, Germany
P46	C–F bond activation of Fluoroalkanes <i>via</i> Germylium Ions catalysis Julie Borel , Humboldt Universität zu Berlin, Germany
P47	INCREASING THE OXIDATION STRENGTH OF POLYNITRILE OXIDIZERS BY COORDINATION TO LEWIS ACIDS AND SYNTHESIS OF A NEW STRONG LEWIS ACID Amina L. Moshtaha , Freie Universität Berlin, Germany
P48	SILVER FLUORIDES IN MIXED OXIDATION STATES (I)/(II) Katarzyna Kuder , University of Warsaw, Poland

BIOORGANIC & MEDICINAL CHEMISTRY

P49	HOW DOES FLUORINE REALLY AFFECT THE PERFORMANCE OF PHARMACEUTICALS? Graham Pattison , University of Lincoln, United Kingdom
P50	SURFACE ENHANCED INFRARED ABSORPTION SPECTROSCOPY ON THE INTERACTION OF CELL PENETRATING PEPTIDES WITH LIPID BILAYERS Ferhat Mutlu , Freie Universität Berlin, Germany
P51	INVESTIGATING THE SITE-SPECIFIC IMPACT OF FLUORINE SUBSTITUTION ON AROMATIC INTERACTIONS IN A TRYPTOPHAN ZIPPER PEPTIDE David Reiter , Freie Universität Berlin, Germany

MATERIALS

P52	POST-METAL-ETCH HF CONDITIONING OF BCAT GATE OXIDE FOR SIMULTANEOUS GIDL SUPPRESSION AND WORD-LINE RESISTANCE RECOVERY IN SUB-10 NM DRAM Jeon Jaehyeon , Sungkyunkwan University, South Korea
P53	FLUORINE GAS GENERATION WITH METAL FLUORIDE REDUCTION Yuki Shukuno , Kyoto University, Japan
P54	FUNCTIONALIZATION OF NANODIAMONDS WITH PERFLUOROPOLYETHER PEROXIDE <i>VIA</i> A FACILE THERMOCHEMICAL PROCESS Davide Ceriotti , Politecnico di Milano, Italy

P55 MECHANOCHEMICAL SYNTHESIS OF FLUORINATED PEROVSKITES $KCuF_3$ and $KNiF_3$

Arianna Collora, Politecnico di Milano, Italy

P56 INVESTIGATION OF DICATIONIC IONIC LIQUIDS WITH DIFLUOROPHOSPHATE ANION

Kentaro Kamada, Kyoto University, Japan

P57 ACTIVATED CARBON FOR PFAS AND PHARMACEUTICAL REMOVAL: A SUSTAINABLE WATER PURIFICATION APPROACH

Beatriz P. Machado, NOVA University Lisbon, Portugal

P58 SUSTAINABLE WATER TREATMENT: REGENERATING ACTIVATED CARBON TO REMOVE EMERGING CONTAMINANTS

Maria G. Vaz, NOVA University Lisbon, Portugal

P59 LEWIS-ACID MEDIATED MECHANOCHEMICAL DEGRADATION OF PVDF

Minh Bui, Humboldt Universität zu Berlin, Germany

P60 OXIDATIVE FLUORINATION OF Cu/ZnO METHANOL CATALYSTS WITH NF_3 AS FLUORINATING AGENT

Henrik Schuster, University of Freiburg, Germany

P61 FLUORINATED HEXOSOME CARRIERS FOR ENHANCED SOLUBILITY OF DRUGS

Tiffany Guitton-Spassky, Freie Universität Berlin, Germany

P62 PERFLUOROCARBON EMISSIONS DURING DYSPROSIUM ELECTROLYSIS FROM FLUORIDE-BASED MELTS

Vesna S. Cvetković, University of Belgrade, Serbia

P63 CF_4/C_2F_6 GASES EMISSIONS DURING RARE EARTH ELECTROLYSIS

Nataša M. Petrović, University of Belgrade, Serbia

COMPUTATIONAL CHEMISTRY

P64 UNDERSTANDING THE KEY FEATURES DRIVING THE SOLUBILITY BEHAVIOR OF F-GASES IN SOLVENTS THROUGH THE SAFT-VR MIE MODEL FOR REFRIGERATION APPLICATIONS

Isaias Huenuvil-Pacheco, Universidad de Concepción, Chile

P65 INVESTIGATING THE ELECTRONIC STRUCTURE OF LANTHANOID TRIFLUORIDES USING X-RAY SPECTROSCOPY AND FIRST PRINCIPLE METHODS

Fabian Goeritz, Freie Universitaet Berlin, Germany

P66 THE BIOINORGANIC IMPACT OF FLUORINE STUDIED BY VIBRATIONAL SPECTROSCOPY

Soumyamoy Pathak, Freie Universitaet Berlin, Germany

P67 SEARCH FOR NOVEL SUPERCONDUCTORS IN A CHEMICAL CAPACITOR SETUP

Dawid Ciszewski, University of Warsaw, Poland

P68 REGIO- AND STEREOCHEMICAL BEHAVIOUR OF CYCLOOCTANE DERIVATIVES CONTAINING CF_2 MOIETIES

Matheus P. Freitas, Federal University of Lavras, Brazil

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P69 PERFLUORINATED (PFAS) POLLUTANTS – MOLECULAR MODELLING AND SIMULATION FOR ENVIRONMENTAL REMEDIATION

Pedro Morgado, Universidade de Lisboa, Portugal

P70 ADSORPTION OF PFOA AND PFOS USING MODIFIED ALUMINA

Friederike Scheller, University of Stuttgart, Germany

P71 HYBRID CONSTRUCTED WETLANDS FOR RUNOFF WATER TREATMENT: EFFICIENCY IN REMOVING ORGANIC POLLUTION AND CONTAMINANTS OF EMERGING CONCERN

Hajer Ennouri, University of Tunis El Manar, Tunisia

P72 DEVELOPMENT AND CHARACTERIZATION OF INNOVATIVE MATERIALS FOR PHOTOCATALYTIC DEGRADATION OF PERFLUOROOCCTANOIC ACID

Kristina Kasalica, University of Belgrade, Serbia

P73 RESPIROMETRIC ANALYSIS FOR MONITORING THE MICROBIAL ACTIVITY DURING EXPOSURE TO PERFLUOROBUTANESULFONIC AND PERFLUOROHXANESULFONIC ACID

Natalija Petronijevic, University of Belgrade, Serbia

P75 FUNGAL BIODEGRADATION OF PFAS: METABOLITE FORMATION AND DEFLUORINATION BY *CUNNINGHAMELLA ELEGANS*

Gaurav Chugh, University College Dublin, Dublin, Ireland

FLUOROUS TECHNOLOGY

P76 ENHANCED DETECTION OF FLUORINATED NANO-PARTICLES IN SEMICONDUCTOR FABRICATION VIA FDTD-OPTIMIZED OPTICAL INSPECTION

Hyoseop Shin, Sungkyunkwan University, Samsung Institute of Technology, South Korea

P77 BASE-MEDIATED POLY-SUBSTITUTION OF POLYFLUOROARENES BY S_NAR WITH TERMINAL ALKYNES AND SUBSEQUENT FLUORIDE TRANSFER

George Cadman, University of Nottingham, UK

P78 Effect of HF Treatment Time on Gate–Dielectric Profile Evolution and Cell Speed in 3D Flash Memory

Chansung Park, Sungkyunkwan University, South Korea

P79 EFFECT OF FLUORINE CONCENTRATION ON SELF-PASSIVATING ETCH PROFILES IN ADVANCED DRAM CONTACT FORMATION

Juyoung Huh, Sungkyunkwan Graduate School, Samsung Electronics, South Korea

P80 OPTIMIZATION OF ASYMMETRIC FIN PROFILES TO MITIGATE ROW HAMMER IN SCALED DRAM THROUGH AN ETCHING PROCESS UTILIZING CF_4

Donggyu Huh, Sungkyunkwan Graduate School, Samsung Electronics, South Korea

P81 SHEDDING LIGHT ON MIXED-GAS SOLUBILITY AND SELF-DIFFUSIVITY OF FLUORINATED REFRIGERANT BLENDS IN IONIC LIQUIDS WITH ^{19}F -NMR

Gabriel Zarca, Universidad de Cantabria, Spain

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